

D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
CERT	Computer Emergency Response Team
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
IA	Innovation Action
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSP	Kaspersky
PMs	Person Months
R&I	Research & Innovation
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 883321, CitySCAPE project aims to systematically explore all different cybersecurity dimensions of multimodal transport. These dimensions will drive a characterization of the cyber-threats in the ICT multimodal transport, extended to the close-by power and financial sector. Innovative software tools will be introduced to estimate the threats propagation in the system. Then, CitySCAPE will realize a modular software toolkit enabled to be seamlessly integrated into any multimodal transport system to:

- a) Detect suspicious traffic-data values and identify persistent threats;
- b) Evaluate an attack's impact in technical and notably in financial terms;
- c) Combine external knowledge and internally-observed activities to enhance the predictability of zero- day attacks;
- d) Instantiate a networked overlay to circulate informative notifications to CERT authorities and support their interplay.

The objectives of Work Package 9 "Training, Awareness and high -impact dissemination" regarding the dissemination activities are multiple. The first is to develop the CitySCAPE Communication Strategy and Plan and ensure it is up to date during the project. Secondly, to establish high quality impactful channels and means for communicating project objectives, activity, progress, impact and outcomes, maximizing its outreach and creating higher level of awareness and demand from multiple stakeholders. Finally, to liaise with relevant R&D initiatives for creating strong cooperation links and exchange knowledge and for ensuring interoperability of developed systems through Europe. This deliverable, D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan outlines the communication strategy we have devised for CitySCAPE along with the plan to ensure significant engagement with key stakeholders and audiences during the project. The deliverable is the main output of Task 9.4 and it will include the communication and dissemination plan to be followed within the project.

The project's communication strategy and plan, is a step-wise process that includes all incremental steps, such as: definition of main objectives for communication and Dissemination, identification of the project key audiences and the messages to be used to reach out to them, the means and channels to be used, the dissemination processes to be followed by individual partners and the initial communication and dissemination tools that are created for maximizing awareness about the project and communicating the proper messages across stakeholders.

The CitySCAPE communication strategy and plan is dynamic and should be adapted both according to time and project results. In the beginning of the project, it is vital to quickly disseminate the project's goal and expected impact. On a later stage, and as project results are becoming available, communication and dissemination activities need to focus on the presentation of these results to specific audiences. Emphasis will be given in activities and channels that will be able to maximise the project 'results' impact while still providing the general project's vision and how this is facilitated.

Communication and dissemination activities are both a partner-specific and a collective task. All partners are expected to take part in these activities on a different scale, appropriate for each partner's role and individual plans within the project.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Introduction

The traditional security controls and security assurance arguments are becoming increasingly inefficient in supporting the emerging needs and applications of the interconnecting transport systems, allowing threats and security incidents to disturb all dimensions of transportation.

CitySCAPE is a project funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, which consists of 15 partners from 6 European countries, united in their vision to cover the cybersecurity needs of multimodal transportation.

More specifically, the CitySCAPE software toolkit will:

- ✓ Detect suspicious traffic-data values and identify persistent threats
- ✓ Evaluate an attack's impact in both technical and financial terms
- ✓ Combine external knowledge and internally-observed activities to enhance the predictability of zero-day attacks
- ✓ Instantiate a networked overlay to circulate informative notifications to CERT/CSIRT authorities and support their interplay.

The project duration extends from September 2020 to August 2023.

1.2 Deliverable Purpose

This deliverable presents an overview of how the communication and dissemination objectives will be achieved and provides the framework to guide communication and dissemination activities within CitySCAPE. It identifies the target groups for dissemination and communication activities and explains how and through which dissemination channels they will be reached. It describes the main dissemination tools to be developed to create awareness and achieve a high level of impact for the project and its results.

All the Consortium's partners must be aware of both communication and dissemination opportunities and procedures. Consequently, this deliverable will provide an initial description of current communication and dissemination opportunities and will describe all the procedures to be followed. The latter are available in [chapter 6.3](#) of the current document and well introduced in the Consortium to ensure coherence and complementarity. All processes and procedures are in accordance with the Consortium Agreement and the H2020 communication and Dissemination guidelines.

1.3 Intended readership

This deliverable is disseminated publicly. The intended readership comprises the CitySCAPE consortium members, the European Commission's Project Officer of CitySCAPE and the general public.

It will be of high interest for the consortium members to use it as a reference for planning the project's dissemination and communication activities and contributing to raising awareness about the project.

1.4 Structure of the Deliverable

The deliverable D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan is comprised of **7 chapters** and **5 annexes**. The first chapter introduces the reader to the CitySCAPE project. It describes the scope of the current deliverable, the audience that is addressed to, its relation to other WP9 deliverables and tasks and defines the key concepts used. The second chapter presents the communication approach and objectives, targeted audiences and the messages that will be used. The third chapter presents the project's identity, whereas the fourth chapter presents the suitable tools and channels planned to be used and sets the success criteria for evaluating the performed dissemination activities per year within the CitySCAPE project. The fifth chapter refers to the problems in projects' Dissemination and communication caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. The sixth chapter presents the CitySCAPE's Consortium's role and forms a roadmap accompanied by a preliminary action plan and informs about the dissemination procedures used within CitySCAPE. Lastly, the seventh chapter concludes this document.

1.5 Relationship with other Deliverables and Tasks

Deliverable	Relationship	Example
D9.7 CitySCAPE Communication tools	It presents all the communication tools and how they will be used throughout the project's lifetime (project brand identity, communication kit, website and social media accounts). The communication tools are part of the communication strategy described in deliverable D9.6.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual identity • Communication kit (brochure, poster, roll-up banner, e-newsletter, video, factsheets) • Website and the social media • Press Activities
D9.8: Report on Communication and Dissemination activities	It includes all the communication and dissemination activities performed to promote the project, along with information and statistics. The deliverable D9.6 provides the context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Events, • Workshops, webinars, conferences, • Mass media activities

and foundation for these activities.

Table 1: Relationship between D9.6 and other deliverables from WP9

Task	Relationship	Example
Task 9.4 CitySCAPE Brand Identity and Communication strategy	Deliverable D9.6 is the main output of Task 9.4	It will ensure appropriate, impactful activities are planned to achieve stakeholder engagement, create awareness and promote CitySCAPE.
Task 9.5 High Impact CitySCAPE communication activities	Within this task, the appropriate communication material will be prepared. Effective means will be developed to properly communicate the project vision and evolutions to all defined target audiences, which will be defined by deliverable D9.6.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication kit (brochure, poster, roll-up banner, e-newsletter, video, factsheets) • Website and the social media • Press Activities • Events, conferences, workshops, Final event

Table 2: Relationship between D9.6 and other Tasks from WP9

1.6 Key Concepts definition

Communication and Dissemination are both key elements of any H2020 project. The table below presents their differences based on the [European IP Helpdesk](#) (Making the most of your H2020 project).

	Communication	Dissemination
Definition	Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of	The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including scientific publications in any medium. <i>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</i>

	audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. <i>(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)</i>	
Objectives	Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g., by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximizing EU-funded research.
Focus	Inform about and promote the project and its results/success.	Describe and ensure results available for others to use. Focus given on results only
Target Audiences	Multiple audiences beyond the 'project's own community incl. Media and the broad public.	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential use of the results (e.g., the scientific community, industrial partners, policymakers).
Formal Obligations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for Participants • RIA & IA Proposal Template 2.2 b) • Grant Agreement Art. 38.1 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rules for Participants • RIA & IA Proposal Template 2.2 a) • Grant Agreement Art. 29

Table 3: Communication and Dissemination definitions and differences

2 COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

The purpose of the CitySCAPE communication strategy is to develop effective communication proposals ensuring that all communication activities address the core objectives agreed and that the key messages are consistently delivered. It is considered of high importance to define a communication strategy from the early stages of the project. In this way, the communication resources could be allocated in the most efficient way to specific activities that will maximize the project's impact on the society.

The communication strategy defines the objectives to be achieved and when the objectives are defined, the key audiences are specified. For different key audiences, a set of key messages are being drafted, tailored to maximize impact. Finally, the various communication channels available to reach out to the key audiences are being discussed, along with the KPIs to monitor the effects of the activities performed.

2.1 Communication Approach

The communication approach of the CitySCAPE is based on a five-step approach that addresses most of the basic elements of communication, namely audience, message, communication means and channels to be used, and the time frame for delivering the messages. It also provides a monitoring and evaluation process to ensure the efficiency of the communication strategy and allow the smooth coordination of all communications activities throughout the project life.

This is achieved by answering some very simple questions, according to the five Ws of "Lasswell's model of communication"¹ such as "**W**ho are the key audiences?", "**W**hich are their needs?", "**W**hat do we need to communicate to them – our messages?", "**W**hat are the most effective channels to deliver these messages?", "**W**hat are the results of our actions?". The implementation of this approach will ensure the project's impact maximization with regard to targeted audiences.

¹ Lasswell, H. (1948). Bryson, L., ed. The Structure and Function of Communication in Society. The Communication of Ideas. New York: Institute for Religious and Social Studies.

Figure 1: The 5-step approach

In terms of time, the CitySCAPE project will follow an approach similar to the one dictated by the project work plan, split into three phases. During the initial phase, the main focus will be on informing the public about the project's concept and main objectives, as well as reaching out to the targeted audiences and specific stakeholder groups. The second phase will build upon the first, evaluating and reviewing initial activities. Moreover, promoting the initial project results in more tailored ways for each of the key stakeholder groups. The main focus will be to effectively communicate available project results and raise further awareness on project-related issues in an engaging way. In the final phase, a major effort will be made to effectively disseminate project results to the targeted audiences to ensure the long-term impact of the project's final results. Within the frame of this deliverable, a communication roadmap and action plan of the project communication and dissemination activities have been devised (see [Chapter 6.2 and Table 6](#) of the current document).

2.2 Communication Objectives

The first and most important step in setting the communication strategy for the CitySCAPE project is to clearly define the objectives to be achieved and then have the associated activities appropriately designed in order to meet those objectives.

According to the Grant Agreement, the Consortium is committed to implementing all the necessary actions from the early beginning to assure CitySCAPE impact, aiming to boost European technology and create a paradigm shift in the core operations of cybersecurity in the multimodal transport sector. The objectives for all communication actions can be summarised as follows:

- Ensuring that all produced communication activities are engaging and interesting to the specific target audiences, showing how the

CitySCAPE technologies and proposed innovations are expected to transform the way multimodal transport operations are being structured.

- Ensure that results influence CERTs/CSIRTs network, transport operators, related decision-makers and public authorities, European and international organizations and networks, by convincing them about the added value for the European cybersecurity multimodal passenger transport sector that the realization of the CitySCAPE innovations brings-in.
- Liaising with relevant EU-funded projects to create strong cooperation links and exchange knowledge and ensure developed systems' interoperability through Europe.
- Raising public awareness about the project's offered solution and how it will positively affect the European citizens' everyday life.
- Informing the European citizens about the value of activities supported by the H2020 program and showing the importance of EU funding in such activities.

2.3 Key Audiences

The definition of the key audiences and the understanding of their special characteristics and needs is critical for directing the resources to the most relevant and interested actors, thus maximizing the project's potential impact.

Key audiences/Communication Channel								
Key audiences → Communication Channel ↓	Decision-makers & Public Authorities	CERT/CSIRTs	Multimodal passenger transportation authorities & operators	Transport software providers & actors	European/international standardization community	European/international organizations & networks for cybersecurity	Academic and scientific actors	General Public
Website		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social media			✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Brochure/poster/roll up banner/factsheets	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Video	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓
Newsletters		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Press Activities	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Presentations in events	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Scientific publications		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	
Final event	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓

Table 4: Media that will be used per target audience

2.4 Key Messages

There is a number of key messages that can be used by the project partners in order to present CitySCAPE. This is useful to provide a coherent branding of the project. The key messages should be considered a baseline, meaning they should be adapted depending on their possible use and the targeted audience.

2.4.1 General Message

The traditional security controls and security assurance arguments are becoming increasingly inefficient in supporting the emerging needs and applications of the interconnecting transport systems, allowing threats and security incidents to disturb all dimensions of transportation.

CitySCAPE is a project funded by the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program, which consists of 15 partners from 6 European countries, united in their vision to cover the cybersecurity needs of multimodal transportation.

More specifically, the CitySCAPE software toolkit will:

- ✓ Detect suspicious traffic-data values and identify persistent threats
- ✓ Evaluate an attack's impact in both technical and financial terms
- ✓ Combine external knowledge and internally-observed activities to enhance the predictability of zero-day attacks
- ✓ Instantiate a networked overlay to circulate informative notifications to CERT/CSIRT authorities and support their interplay.

2.4.2 Key Words

Interoperable secured communications (Security systems architecture), Risks and vulnerabilities assessment, Cybersecurity, Communication technologies, Information Security Technologies, Cybersecurity for Cloud-based services, Attack modeling and security assurance tools, City-transport passengers privacy, Threats investigation and impact assessment, Standards, Cybersecurity training, Collaborative platforms.

2.4.3 Tailored Key Messages

In the table below, different key messages per target audience are being presented. The target audiences are:

1. Decision-makers & Public Authorities,
2. CERT/CSIRTs,
3. Multimodal passenger transportation authorities & operators,
4. Transport software providers & actors

5. European/international standardization community,
6. European/international organizations & networks for cybersecurity,
7. Academic & scientific actors,
8. General Public

Target Audience	Key Message
1,2,3,4,6,7	CitySCAPE provides forecasting mechanism, based on past events and actions to predict an attack or a possible event that may affect the activities of an urban mobility system.
1,2,3,4,6,7	CitySCAPE toolkit addresses the whole cycle of the cybersecurity challenges emerging in city-level transport from the identification of the involved assets and vulnerabilities up to the collaborative incident investigation and impact assessment of a possible attack.
1,2,6	The CitySCAPE platform will be capable of sharing information coming from different sources and therefore will achieve the maximization of the CSIRT network added value.
1,2,3,4,6,7	CitySCAPE toolkit allows users to estimate the attack impact in both technology and financial levels that drives a cost-benefit analysis on potential further investments to cybersecurity and privacy countermeasures.
1,2,3,4,5,6,7	CitySCAPE will promote best practices in cybersecurity management solutions to the multimodal transport community and through training of security experts will seek to communicate their value and thus, increase their acceptance
1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8	CitySCAPE enhances the cybersecurity level of the urban transport systems contributing to their uninterrupted operation.
1,4,8	The digitalization of transports is a process that must respect the security and safety of the users as a priority. Therefore, the success of CitySCAPE is a big step towards the achievement of safe, reliable and efficient transport systems.
4,8	CitySCAPE platform will enable a fully protected transport ecosystem, improving journeys.

Table 5. Key message per target audience

3 PROJECT IDENTITY

3.1 Brand identity

The CitySCAPE project will build a strong project identity through effective branding and delivering clear messages to a variety of target audiences. To this end, a project's logo, project's templates and a dedicated brand book were created to create a consistent appearance that will be used throughout the whole project in all applicable communication and Dissemination channels (website, leaflets, poster, templates, and presentations). This is the most effective way to ensure that a consistent identity of CitySCAPE is widely communicated.

3.1.1 Logo

A dedicated logo has been agreed upon by the project's partners from the beginning of the project in order to act as a trademark, promote instant public recognition and trigger reactions from the viewers even from the first performed communication and dissemination activities.

CitySCAPE's logo was chosen to be simple, easily recognizable and self-explanatory so that people could immediately understand the main idea of the project. The logo presents the most important means of transport that will be used in the two project's pilot demonstrations and a padlock as well as a wireless internet symbol that show the cybersecurity aspect of the project.

In addition, a dedicated brand book was created in order to ensure the proper use of the logo, maintaining the integrity of the project's brand identity. The brand book contains several logo variations, the color pallet guide, the logo proper and improper use, the social media usage and the brand typography. The brand book is available in the [Redmine Work Space](#) and the CitySCAPE [website](#).

Figure 2: CitySCAPE logo

Figure 3: CitySCAPE brand book

3.1.2 Colour Palette

The CitySCAPE logo is made up of a range of colors that were carefully chosen and specified from the very beginning of the project. Keeping the project's colors cohesive in print and digital use creates a strong and consistent visual presence.

Figure 4: CitySCAPE color palette

3.1.3 Templates

A set of CitySCAPE MS office templates has been created based on the project brand in order to be used in all internal and external events. More specifically, a PowerPoint presentation template has been developed to be used both for the project internal meetings and for the external audience. Moreover, a word Deliverable template has been prepared for submitting the CitySCAPE deliverables and a Meeting Minutes template for keeping minutes within the Consortium's meetings. All the templates are available to all partners on the [Redmine Work Space](#). They are also presented in [Annex I](#) of this document.

4 COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

This section provides a brief overview of the CitySCAPE communication tools. A fully detailed presentation of them will be given in the deliverable D9.7 Communication Tools that will be ready by M18. The KPIs agreed in the GA for each tool separately are also presented.

4.1 Online Tools

4.1.1 Website

The project's [website](#) is the most important communication channel of the project and it will serve as a key element of engagement with the identified key audiences. The website will present the project's general description, its objectives and impact, its partners, events and news. All the public deliverables and scientific publications will be uploaded along with the CitySCAPE dissemination material and the newsletters, which will be downloadable. Finally, there is a Blog section in which partners are asked to write an article based on the work they have performed or will perform within the project. These articles will also be used in the E-newsletters and the project's social media. To ensure smooth production of articles by the partners, a time plan has been created and circulated among the partners. It is also presented in [Annex 2](#) of this document. More details about the website will be presented in deliverable D9.7 Communication Tools that will be submitted in M18.

KPI: 1 website

Figure 5: CitySCAPE website

4.1.2 Social Media

The project will make extended use of social media platforms, namely Twitter and LinkedIn, in order to create awareness around CitySCAPE, to communicate the project's progress and its results, and to diffuse the

project's news and activities. Besides that, all partners are encouraged to promote the project through their organizations' social media and have agreed on having at least four posts regarding CitySCAPE on their social media; this action is also mentioned in the GA.

4.1.2.1 Twitter

Twitter is a social networking platform that is ideal for spreading news and engaging with users in real-time. [@EUCityscape](#) is interacting with relevant accounts and promoting the project's vision and progress.

KPI: 1st year → 150 followers

3rd year → 500 followers

Figure 6: CitySCAPE Twitter account

4.1.2.2 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the most popular professional network on the internet. Registered members are able to establish connections with professionals who are in their interest and interact in group discussions. [CitySCAPE LinkedIn](#) account will enable to build a strong network with some of the project's key audiences, such as research institutes, industry, policymakers and individuals involved in the cybersecurity and transport sector.

KPI: 1st year → 150 followers

3rd year → 500 followers

Figure 7: CitySCAPE LinkedIn page

4.1.3 Social Media Hashtags

A hashtag is prefaced by the hash symbol, #. Hashtags as a way to connect social media content to a specific topic, event, theme or conversation. They also make it easier to discover posts around those specific topics because hashtags aggregate all social media content with that same hashtag. The usage of specific hashtags will help to increase the post's visibility and the followers' engagement to the posts.

The hashtags used by CitySCAPE are: #H2020, #CyberSecurity, #Transport #multimodaltransport, #EUfunded, #EUresearch

4.2 Communication Kit

4.2.1 Brochure, Poster, Roll up banner

The CitySCAPE first version of the brochure, poster and roll-up banner are available in [Redmine Work Space](#) and the CitySCAPE [website](#) for all partners to use at conferences, workshops, meetings and events. The content of the brochure was kept as simple as possible while an effort was made for an attractive design. It contains all the details and possible information an interested third party would like to know about the project, including contact and project's details, the project's impact and objectives, the CitySCAPE architecture, the starting date and the duration of the project, the EU funding, the project's social media accounts, as well as information regarding the consortium and a QR code that points at the project's website. In more detail, the leaflet includes the following sections:

- What is CitySCAPE about?
- Objectives
- Expected Impact
- CitySCAPE At a Glance
- Get Connected

The poster and the roll-up banner explain shortly the solution that will be provided by the CitySCAPE project. Moreover, they contain all the important information about the project, including the starting date and the duration of the project, the EU funding, the contact details of the project coordinator

as well as the links to the project's social media accounts, information about the consortium and a QR code that points at the project's website.

A second version of the material will be produced towards the end of the project. The first version of the brochure, poster and roll-up banner are also shown in [Annex 3](#) of this document.

KPI: 2 brochures, 2 posters, 2 roll up banners

4.2.2 Pilot Factsheets

CitySCAPE will create pilot factsheets for each of the CitySCAPE pilot use cases that will be held in Genova, Italy and Tallinn, Estonia. The factsheets will be available in the last year of the project to proclaim the pilot outcomes and they will be created both in English and in the local languages, namely in Italian and Estonian

KPI: 3rd year → 2 Pilot Factsheets (English and Estonian, English and Italian)

4.2.3 Video

One CitySCAPE general video, including animations or interviews and live footage, will have been created by the end of CitySCAPE with the basic aim to visually explain project solutions to non-technical audiences and the general public.

KPI: by M36 → 1 video

4.2.4 E-newsletters

Five e-newsletters will be issued around major milestones starting from M12. The e-newsletters will be sent to the CitySCAPE Stakeholders' Community members and will be published on the CitySCAPE website and the project's social media. There is a dedicated section on the CitySCAPE website in which people can register for the newsletter.

KPI: 5 e-newsletters by M36

4.3 Press Activities

The project's press releases will be developed by ICCS upon specific project's achievements to several media communication channels such as local or national radio, television and online press. A kick-off press release had been created and is available on the CitySCAPE [website](#). Moreover, the press release was published in Greek by ICCS and in Italian by KSP. Both the press releases and their press clippings in many online media are available in the [Media Center](#) section of the CitySCAPE website.

The CitySCAPE partners will use their press contacts to communicate the developments of the project and will be responsible for translations and regional adaptations. Partners efforts will also focus on publishing major CitySCAPE achievements through channels and means offered by the European Commission (i.e., the Horizon Magazine, research*EU results magazine, Futuris Magazine etc.)

As it is mentioned in the CitySCAPE GA, Article 38, before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the Agency. Therefore, whenever a communication activity that is expected to reach the general public (not the specialized press or media) like an interview of the Coordinator for the national TV, an article in a national newspaper, etc., is scheduled, the project coordinator should inform the Project Officer.

KPI: N/A

4.4 Events

4.4.1 Conferences and other events

CitySCAPE plans to organize its own dissemination events as well as take advantage of other established highly recognizable Cyber-Security, ICT, transport sector conferences, fairs and meetings events to present project results to a wider audience. The list of identified international conferences and related events where CitySCAPE may present its outcomes is available in the [Redmine Work Space](#). The list will be regularly updated to include further dissemination opportunities, while relevant information will be sent to the Consortium on a regular basis via direct mailing.

KPI: 4 presentations per year and 12 presentations by M36

4.4.2 Networking and stakeholder engagement activities

ICCS as the leader of Task 9.5, will identify relevant organizations and networks of high interest for the project mostly through organizations, associations and networks in most of which CitySCAPE partners already participate. Moreover, strong liaison activities will be established between the CitySCAPE project and other EU-funded projects such as E-CORRIDOR, 2CeVau and more. Possible collaboration in joint workshops or webinars and events will be sought wherever possible. Exchange of project results and the organization of common webinars and special sessions in popular conferences are planned as liaison activities.

Finally, project results will also be presented by the partners in respective associations, organizations, fora and in highly recognizable exhibitions that are participating such as CYBERSEC FORUM, ENISA, General Cybersecurity Conference, Black-Hat Europe etc.

KPI: 5 presentations per year and 15 presentations by M36; 3 special sessions; 3 stands and/or demonstrations

4.4.3 Final Event

At the end of the project (between M33-M36), the CitySCAPE final event will be held with the basic purpose to widely disseminate the CitySCAPE final results and outcomes among the related target audiences and expert communities and push exploitation and adoption of CitySCAPE after the project closure.

KPI: 1 final event by M36

4.5 Publications

CitySCAPE will make a major effort in publishing peer-reviewed scientific papers in high-impact factor peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings. CitySCAPE will sustain the Gold and Green Model, upon which publishing peer-reviewed scientific articles resulting from the project will be available in the open-access model. To assist partners in planning their dissemination activities, a list, including prestigious journals, has been distributed to the Consortium and is available in the [Redmine Work Space](#). This document will be regularly updated to include further dissemination opportunities, while relevant information will be sent to the Consortium on a regular basis via direct mailing. Partners have been strongly advised to use

[Open Research Europe](#), the new open access publishing platform, for the publication of research stemming from Horizon 2020 funding.

The list of accepted and submitted publications by the CitySCAPE partners will also be maintained and updated.

KPI: 4 papers in conference proceedings; at least 1 publication in a scientific journal

5 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Communication and dissemination actions are an important pillar of the CitySCAPE project and the Consortium will ensure that the action will be delivered despite the challenges created by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, most of the conferences and events of 2020 were canceled or were transferred on different dates of 2021. However, after the first shock, fortunately, many conferences and events have become virtual and they are being held with no problem.

Therefore, until the cease of the pandemic, the project will participate in digital format events, will organize webinars along with other EU-funded projects, even though it is not mentioned in the GA, and will focus on its virtual presence through online media, its website and social media.

6 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

6.1 Partners' role

ICCS is the WP9 leader and responsible for managing and monitoring the communication and dissemination activities. ICCS will be engaging with all project partners to ensure that the communication and dissemination activities of the project are effective and impactful. All partners will contribute to the communication and dissemination activities of the project by using all their available networks and communication channels, including websites, press contacts, social networking webpages etc. and through their participation in the main international events, publishing research papers and articles in journals and conferences.

Partner	WP9 PMs
ICCS	23
ACS	8
ED	4
KSP	20
TALLINN	8
CERT-EE	9
AMT	9
STAM	1
SIGLA	5
UPRC	1
OPP	1
ASI	4
CS	1
ENG	1
Taltech	1

Table 6: WP9 PMs per partner

All partners were asked to plan their dissemination activities (participation in events, social media presence) regarding the first phase (M1-M12) of the project's lifetime and fill in the appropriate forms. The template is presented in [Annex 4](#) of this document and the filled forms are available in the [Redmine Work Space](#). The same procedure will be followed for the next two project's phases (M12-M24 & M24-M36)

6.2 Roadmap and preliminary action plan

A communication roadmap has been determined for the whole duration of the project. It is presented below and it provides an outline of the way that the communications channels and tools will be used for reaching each of the specified key audiences per year of the project. Moreover, a preliminary action plan is presented, showing the planned actions that will be performed per activity in order to have a complete and successful communication of the project and reach the KPIs agreed in the GA.

However, not all the communication actions are yet planned and changes are likely to occur as the project evolves.

Phase & Months	Description	Communication Activities	Planned Actions per activity for successful communication & reaching KPIs	Milestones & Deliverables
<p style="text-align: center;">1st phase M1-12</p>	<p>In the initial phase of the project, more emphasis will be given to the communication activities. The dissemination activities will be more intense toward the end of this phase when the initial project's results will be available. Dissemination activities will focus on raising awareness and providing information to relevant stakeholders about the project's concept and expected impact and the initial project's results</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of brand identity (project logo, brand story with guidelines, illustrations and graphics, templates) • Creation of the communication kit • Creation of project website and constant content update • Set up of social media channels and continuous networking • Publication of media articles/interviews • Publication of press releases • Project presentations in conferences and other events • Project presentations in respective associations, organizations, fora and exhibitions • Establishing Liaison & networking activities with related projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brand identity ready before KoM • 1st version of the brochure, poster, roll-up banner ready by M3 • Website launch by M3 • Social Media ready before KoM and 150 followers by M12 • 2 media articles/interviews • 1 press release • 4 project presentations in several events, 1 special session • 5 project presentations in respective associations, organizations etc • Connect with at least 2 EU projects 	<p>MS14 (M3) D9.6 (M6)</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">2nd phase M12-24</p>	<p>Communication activities will aim to communicate and publish the results and</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website and social media updates • Project presentations in conferences and other events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly updates on the website & social media, reach 300 followers 	<p>D9.7 (M18)</p>

	<p>developments available.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project presentations in respective associations, organizations, fora and exhibitions • Publication of media articles/interviews • Peer-reviewed publications in conference proceedings and scientific journals • Continuing the Liaison & networking activities • Creation & publication of E-newsletter • Creation of Pilot Factsheet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 project presentations in several events • 5 project presentations in respective associations, organizations etc • 2 media articles/interviews (at least 1 in an EU media) • 2 peer-reviewed publications • the organisation of a joint webinar, organization of a joint special session with other projects • 2 or 3 e-newsletters issues published • 1 fact sheet after the 1st Pilot in Tallinn, in English and Estonian 	
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<p style="text-align: center;">3rd phase M24-36</p>	<p>In the final phase of the project, a major effort will be made in effectively disseminating the final project's results to the target audiences to maximize the exploitation and future use of the outcomes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website & social media updates • Communication kit update • Production of the video • Project presentations in conferences and other events • Project presentations in respective associations, organizations, fora and exhibitions • Publication of media articles/interviews • Peer-reviewed publications in conference proceedings and scientific journals • Publication of press releases • Continuing the liaison activities • E-newsletters • Pilot Factsheet • Final event 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weekly updates on the website & social media, reach 500 followers • 1 general video • 4 project presentations in several events • 5 project presentations in respective associations, organizations etc • 2 media articles/interviews (at least 1 in an EU media) • 2 peer-reviewed publications • 1 press release • 1 joint special session or 1 joint webinar with other EU projects • 2 or 3 e-newsletters issues published • 1 Pilot factsheet after the 2nd Pilot in Genova, in English and Italian • 1 Final event 	<p>MS15 (M36) D9.8 (M36)</p>
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Table 7: CitySCAPE roadmap and action plan

6.3 Dissemination Procedures

The participation of consortium partners in any event with an opportunity for Dissemination and promotion of (conferences, workshops, etc.), as well as the performance of every dissemination activity related to CitySCAPE (presentations, paper submissions, material distribution etc.), has to be communicated beforehand to the Dissemination Manager in order to ensure high-quality CitySCAPE publications, presentations and other communication material, avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information and lastly, monitor and record the project's communication and dissemination activities and their impact in an effective way.

The step-by-step procedure was sent to the Consortium and is still available for all in the [Redmine Work Space](#). It is also available in [Annex 5](#) of this document.

6.4 EU Acknowledgement

There are three types of acknowledgments that have to be added depending on the type of materials produced:

1. The following acknowledgment text should be included in **all publications related to the CitySCAPE work**:

"This work is a part of the CitySCAPE project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 883321. This content reflects only the authors' views and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information this publication contains."

2. For **other communication activities**, please add the EC emblem (flag) available [here](#), with the following sentence:

"This work is a part of the CitySCAPE project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 883321. The content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains."

3. For **infrastructure, equipment and major results**, please add the EC emblem (flag) and the following sentence:

"This [infrastructure] [equipment] [insert type of result] is part of the CitySCAPE project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 883321. Content reflects only the authors' view and European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains."

7 CONCLUSION

CitySCAPE is considered to have a major impact on the cybersecurity sector of multimodal transportation. To maximize this impact, the project results will be communicated to a wide scientific community, multimodal passenger transportation authorities & operators, CERT/CSIRTs, transport software providers & actors, the European and international standardization community, as well as the general public.

This deliverable D9.6 Communication Strategy and Plan layouts the scene for the project communication and dissemination activities by elaborating on the approach to be followed and its respective objectives, describing the key audiences for the project and conveying appropriate key messages to reach out to them and by defining the key communication and Dissemination channels and activities to be employed.

CitySCAPE will apply a multi-disciplinary communication and dissemination approach. A set of communication and dissemination tools are (and will be) in place to serve communication and dissemination purposes. These include, but are not limited to: brochures, posters and roll-up banners, Pilot factsheets, e-newsletters, a video, press releases, social media presence, workshops and events. All dissemination and communication activities will be monitored and evaluated across well-defined KPIs to ensure maximum impact of project results.

The Communication Strategy and Plan will be dynamic and will be adapted according to the different project cycles. The overall goal is to ensure the impact of the project results through tailored and well-targeted activities.

ANNEX 1: CitySCAPE Templates

Figure 8: CitySCAPE ppt template 1st slide

Figure 9: CitySCAPE ppt template last slide

Figure 10: CitySCAPE deliverable template

Figure 11: CitySCAPE meeting minutes template

ANNEX 2: Blog Articles Time Plan

Partner	Month
ICCS	February 2021 & June 2022
ACS	March 2021 & July 2022
ED	April 2021 & September 2022
KSP	December 2021 & October 2022
TALLINN	December 2021 & after M26

CERT-EE	June 2021 & November 2022
AMT	May 2022 & April
STAM	September 2021 & January 2023
SIGLA	October 2021 & February 2023
UPRC	November 2021 & March 2023
OPP	January 2022 & April 2023
ASI	February 2022 & May 2023
CS	March 2022 & June 2023
ENG	April 2022 & July 2023
Taltech	May 2022 & August 2023

Table 8: Blog's' articles time plan

ANNEX 3: CitySCAPE Dissemination Material

What is CitySCAPE About?

The Challenge
The traditional security controls and security assurance arguments are becoming increasingly inefficient in supporting the emerging needs and applications of the multimodal transport systems, allowing threats and security incidents to disturb all dimensions of transportation. Therefore, the enormous potential of the multimodal ecosystem, namely a more efficient transportation, which lies on the extent to which it globally remains cyber-secure, is becoming vulnerable.

The CitySCAPE Solution
CitySCAPE introduces innovative risk analysis techniques and orchestrates a number of software solutions to realize an interoperable toolkit that seamlessly integrates to any multimodal transport system.

More specifically, the CitySCAPE software toolkit will:

- Detect suspicious traffic-data values and identify persistent threats
- Evaluate an attack's impact in both technical and financial terms
- Combine external knowledge and internally-observed activities to enhance the predictability of zero-day attacks
- Instantiate a networked overlay to circulate informative notifications to CERT/CSIRT authorities and support their interplay.

Consortium

CitySCAPE At a Glance

Project Facts

Duration: 36 months
(September 2020- August 2023)

EU funding: 4 998 057.88€

Pilots: Tallinn, Estonia / Genova, Italy

Project Coordinator:
Dr Angelos Amditis,
Institute of Communication
and Computer Systems
(ICCS) a.amdits@iccs.gr

Get Connected

This work is a part of the CitySCAPE project. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Figure 12: CitySCAPE brochure

Figure 14: CitySCAPE poster

Figure 13: CitySCAPE roll-up banner

ANNEX4: Partners' Individual Dissemination/Communication Plans Template

Dissemination/Communication plan

To be completed by the CitySCAPE partners once a year

A) Participation in Events

Participation in events (Conferences, Trade shows, Workshops)			
Planned activities			
Period: Sept 2020 – Sept 2021			
No.	Name of the event <i>(which event)</i>	Date <i>(when)</i>	Place <i>(Where)</i>
			What to present

B) Organization of CitySCAPE event

Organization of CitySCAPE event			
Planned activities			
Period: Sept 2020 – Sept 2021			
No.	Date <i>(when)</i>	Partners involved	Description of the event <i>(type, aim)</i>

C) Publications

Publications (journals, conference proceedings paper)			
Planned activities			
Period: Sept 2020 – Sept 2021			
No.	Targeted journals / Conferences	Place <i>(where)</i>	Topic planned to be elaborated <i>(what)</i>
			Other partners to be involved as co-authors <i>(name ONLY the organisation)</i>

D) Social Media

Social media (posts mentioning CitySCAPE project) on individual social media accounts		
G.A mentions at least 4 per partner		
Social media (eg Twitter)	Official account <i>(@ISENSE GROUP)</i>	Number of posts

Figure 15 : CitySCAPE partners' individual dissemination/communication plans template

ANNEX 5: Step By Step Communication Procedure

Step by step procedure

- When an opportunity is identified, please:
 - notify the Dissemination Manager Ms Maria Tsirigoti (maria.tsirigoti@iccs.gr) of your intention by email **at least 15 working days in advance**, and
 - register the activity in the dedicated excel file "[Dissemination Register Requests](#)", specifying the details of the activity (type of activity, date, title, audience) and your role in it related to the CitySCAPE project (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, author etc.).

Prior notice is needed to update the Upcoming Event section of the CitySCAPE website and to allow cross-checking for overlaps and conflicts.

- The Dissemination Manager sends the request within 2 days to the Steering Committee and the Project Security Officer for approval, modification and request for extra information/clarifications or rejection.
- The Steering Committee has to reply to the Dissemination manager within 10 working days; no response is considered as an approval.

4. The Dissemination manager informs the initiator of the dissemination activity and the Project Coordinator about the decision.

In case of **Approval**

The initiator may proceed with the submission or realisation of the planned dissemination activity.

5. After your participation, send a short abstract (content of the session/presentation/discussion, quotes from speakers, highlights, relevant information related to CitySCAPE, size and type of audience reached) to the Dissemination Manager to update the News section of the website.

In case of **Conflict or objection**

6. The WP Leader, after consultation with the Dissemination Manager and in collaboration with the Coordinator, can reject the proposed activity if they have objections related to overlaps or possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information concerning the work performed in the different WPs. In case of conflict, the Dissemination Manager and the involved partners will further discuss.

*If a conflict is created or further material is needed, the Dissemination Manager will inform the partner that modifications or additions are required. Then, the material is proposed again **within 5 working days** to the Dissemination Manager and the respective Task Leader and if significant changes (that might provoke conflicts among partners' interests) must be made, the previous procedure is followed.*

Dissemination activities report

Within **5 working days** after the implementation of the approved dissemination activity, the partner should fill in the dedicated excel file "[Dissemination Register Completed Actions](#)" and store the dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.) in the [dedicated folder](#) set up in the Redmine.

If possible, the Partner should provide the Dissemination Manager with **at least two photos** of their participation to the event/conference/workshop to feed the CitySCAPE website and collect relevant material to use throughout the project implementation.

NOTE:

- If the content is for an external meeting or for publication, but the same material has already been approved and presented elsewhere, the procedure should still be followed. This is to make sure that the Dissemination Manager is informed of any additional change to the material, or if the material has remained unchanged. The

approval would normally be expected as default, unless there was a change in circumstances or if other partners felt the particular event or publication forum (website, etc.) was somehow not suitable for our project. In case a partner wishes to organise a workshop or special event related to CitySCAPE, the approval of the Dissemination manager is needed **3 months** before the realisation of this dissemination activity.

- **GDPR:** If the material contains a reference to other partners or the name or photo of an individual, publishing this content should be agreed with the person/partner in question before the dissemination request is made.

Language: If the material is in a national language other than English, the procedure should still be followed. A brief description in English should be added (not a complete translation). Any other partners who understand the same language are especially invited to comment.
